

C++ PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE OPERATOR USAGE AND THEIR TYPES AND MAIN FUNCTIONS

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Abstract: This article provides information about the use of operators of c# and .net core platform c# programming language and their types and main tasks.

Keywords: NET Framework, C# Language, C++ Runtime, SDK Runtime, Java.

Programming languages are used for a variety of purposes, from solving complex mathematical problems, performing economic-mathematical calculations to creating musical scores and computer graphics. Research on the creation of modern programming languages has been carried out since the time of programming itself. As a result of this research, Microsoft developed the C# language, which meets modern programming standards and is designed to support the development of the .NET Framework technology. In recent years, the C# language and its associated environment, the .NET platform, have been a major new technology for software developers. Through the .NET platform, it is possible to create arbitrary programs that can be created in the Windows environment. The C# language is considered a new language and was specially developed for this environment. Using the C# language, you can create dynamic WEB pages, programs based on multiple technologies, database components, or windowed Windows programs. In addition to network or Internet applications, the C# language can be used to create any program that runs on the Windows platform. It is intended to improve the methodology of creating programs in the Windows environment through the C# and .NET platform.

C#'s relationship to the .NET Framework: Although C# can be studied in isolation as a programming language, it is preferable to consider its interaction with the .NET Framework environment in which it operates. Because first, C# was originally developed by Microsoft to create the .NET Framework code, and second, the .NET Framework defines a library used by the C# language. Since they are so closely related, it is important to understand the general concept of the .NET Framework and its relevance to C#.

.NET Framework– this platform can be interpreted as an environment that supports the development and execution of independent annotations. It allows

you to work together in the annotations of different programming languages, and also provides common programming models and programs for Windows. It should be noted that the .NET Framework is not limited by the Windows platform, and programs written for this platform may be ported to another platform in the future.

C# uses two important components of the .NET Framework:

The first is a system independent of the language execution environment (Common Language Runtime - CLR), which controls the execution of the program and is considered part of the .NET Framework technology, allows switching to programs, supports programming using several languages - and ensures the security of data transmission.

The second is a .NET class library that allows component programs to access the runtime environment, such as for input/output. If you are new to programming, you may be unfamiliar with the concept of a class. Classes will be discussed in more detail in later chapters, but for now we will simply mention that classes are object-oriented constructs that help organize programs. While application properties are currently limited to a specific library of .NET classes, it can be used anywhere the .NET runtime supports it.

.NET code execution is controlled by the language-independent runtime environment (Common Language Runtime - CLR). When we compile a C# program, we get not executable code, but a file consisting of a special pseudocode called Microsoft Intermediate Language (MSIL). The MSIL language defines a set of instructions independent of the processor, that is, in essence, MSIL defines an assembly language. Intermediate Microsoft language is similar in content to Java bytecode, but there are differences between them.

The CLR translates intermediate code to executable code when the program is started. Any program compiled in MSIL can be run on any operating system that implements the CLR environment.

The intermediate Microsoft language is converted to executable code using the Just In Time (JIT) compiler (see Just In Time - just in case). The process works as follows: when a .NET program is executed, the CLR activates the JIT compiler, which converts the MSIL into the internal code of the processor, so that the code of the parts of the program is only translated as needed. So a C# program actually executes as native code, even though it was originally compiled in MSIL. This means that the program's runtime may actually appear as if it were compiled into internal code all at once.

The advantage of MSIL is the portability of the program. In addition, compiling a C# program takes a metadata component that describes what is added to the MSIL, used by the program, and allows the code to interact with other code. Metadata is stored in files that contain MSIL.

Figure 2.1.1. List of programs that can be built in C# based on the .NET platform

In fact, knowledge of the CLR environment, MSIL, and metadata is sufficient for the implementation of the main part of the programming problem in C#, which the language independently organizes the work as needed.

.NET languages: C#, F#, Visual Basic languages can be used to develop .NET applications.

Loading .NET

It is well known that 3 types of .NET Frameworks are the most widely used.

- .NET Framework;
- .NET Core;
- .NET5.

All three Frameworks have an SDK and Runtime. .NET SDK - enables the application to be built and run. The .NET Runtime is what makes the application run, but the SDK also includes the Runtime.

It is well known that applications written on the .NET platform require .NET Runtimes to run. Unlike C++, it cannot be run on any computer, which means that C++ Runtimes exist when Windows is freshly installed on a computer. Therefore, there is no query when running applications written in C++. New versions of Windows now install the .NET Framework.

Let's say I'm a developer and I've developed an application in .NET (C#), or I've created an application that looks like a messenger. I transferred it to my friend's computer. And my friend is not a programmer. Also, it doesn't install the .NET SDK, the SDK is only needed by the developer. Because it is necessary to load (build) the written code. And the average person doesn't write code. A common non-programmer is given the .NET Runtime. That is, he installs the Runtime program on his computer, there will be no problem opening our program. Otherwise it says Install the .NET Framework.

Let's look at the differences between these frameworks.

Through this framework, .NET applications can be developed only for the Windows operating system. There are different versions of .NET Frameworks and these are currently built up to 4.8.

.NET Core: While .NET was trending, a debate arose between Java and .NET developers because C# is Microsoft's Java. It was only possible to write an application on Windows OS using C#. After these problems, Microsoft also developed its own Cross-Platform Framework. It was called .NET Core. Through this Framework, it was possible to create applications for Windows, Linux, MacOS, Docker OS. Later, many developers switched to .NET Core. And getting .NET Framework code into .NET Core could be problematic. If there are only Windows workers, then there is no problem.

.NET5: Many developers work on .NET Core and the rest on .NET Framework. Some services, packages, or libraries were written in the .NET Framework, many of which were not yet ported to .NET Core. There may be some problem with using the library. Because their construction does not match. There was only one way to do it, and that was to convert the .NET Framework project to .NET Core. The conversion is still not optimal. Then they started developing .NET5. Many external contributors (volunteer programmers) were involved for this. It is still a work in progress. It can also be called .NET Framework + .NET Core when explaining Framework in simple terms. That is, now things have become more standardized. If the project is written in .NET5, it can receive services from any framework. If someone writes libraries in Core or Framework, they can easily be imported and used through .NET5. All (C#) developers are moving to .NET5 now, except for a few geeks.

Windows
Linux
macOS
Docker

.NET

.NET 5.0 (recommended)

Current

.NET is a free, cross-platform, open-source developer platform for building many different types of applications.

Download .NET SDK x64

Download .NET Runtime

[All .NET downloads](#)

.NET Core

.NET Core 3.1

LTS

.NET Core is a free, cross-platform, open-source developer platform for building many different types of applications.

Download .NET Core SDK x64

Download .NET Core Runtime

[All .NET Core downloads](#)

.NET Framework

.NET Framework 4.8

.NET Framework is a Windows-only version of .NET for building any type of app that runs on Windows.

Download .NET Framework Dev Pack

Download .NET Framework Runtime

[All .NET Framework downloads](#)

Figure 2.1.2. .Net's main platforms

Below are the links to download the SDK and Runtime for .NET Framework by simply scanning the QR code.

Link to download .NET Framework Dev Pack (SDK):

Link to download .NET Framework Runtime:

Below are the links to download the SDK and Runtime for .NET Core by scanning the QR code.

Link to download .NET Core SDK:

NET Core Runtime Download Link:

Below are the links to download the SDK and Runtime for .NET by simply scanning the QR code.

Link to download .NET SDK:

Link to download .NET Runtime:

A brief introduction to C# and Java programming

Java is an object-oriented (Object-Oriented) and class-based (class-based) programming language. Developers write code in Java once, run it anywhere. Java source code (source), Java compiler converts it to bytecode (bytecode), and then this compiled bytecode makes it possible to work on any operating system using JRE (Java Runtime Environment).

C# is also one of the main languages that are object-oriented (Object-Oriented), functional, general and component-oriented (generic and component-oriented). This language is used to create various programs. This language is a very powerful language for creating Windows programs and games in the Windows operating system (windows application). Web application development can be done efficiently using C# and it is also becoming increasingly popular for mobile application development.

Below are the top 7 comparisons between Java and C#:

MAIN DIFFERENCES

- Java - Runs on the Java Runtime Environment (JRE), while C# is designed to run on the Common Language Runtime (CLR).
- Java is class-based, that is, an object-oriented language based on classes, while C# is a class-based object-oriented, functional, and component-oriented language.
- Java does not support operator overloading, while C# provides multiple operator overloading.
- Java does not support pointers, while C# does only in unsafe mode.
- In Java, arrays belong to the Object library, while in C#, arrays belong to the System library.

Some features of C# and Java programming languages are given in the table below.

Characteristics	Java	c#
Production	Developed by Sun Microsystems.	Developed as part of Microsoft .NET.
Ecosystem	It has a huge open source code system.	Used to develop software for Microsoft platforms.
Delegates	Requires the use of an	C# has its own set of

	interface to achieve delegate-like functionality.	delegates that act as methods.
Exceptions (code reviewing)	An exception has only one type.	Distinguishes between checked and unchecked exceptions.
Goto	Java does not support this operator.	C# supports this operator.
Polymorphism	In the base class it calls the "virtual" keyword and in the derived class it uses the "override" keyword.	Enables polymorphism by default.
Security	Protected.	Unprotected.
Does it support incremental compilation?	Java does not support incremental compilation.	C# supports an additional compilation feature using processor instructions.
Cross-platform	Java is cross-platform enough with its bytecode.	C# is also cross-platform, but compared to Java, it needs to develop this feature.
IDE	Eclipse, NetBeans, IntelliJ IEDA.	Visual Studio, MonoDevelop, Sharp Develop, VS Code.
Runtime	Java runs code using the JVM (Java Virtual Machine).	C# runs code using the CLR (Common Language Runtime).

Advantages of Java

1. Each and every Java code is explained in detail.
2. A certain part of the programmers are Java specialists.
3. Java has a multithreading environment that allows you to perform many tasks at the same time.
4. Libraries are easy to manage.

Advantages of C#

1. Supports appropriate lambdas and generics.
2. Supported by Microsoft Corporation.
3. Automatically separates unnecessary codes and issues a warning.

4. Fields come with get and set blocks. This makes writing code in C# even easier.

5. Automatic memory management is possible.

Disadvantages of Java

1. The JIT compiler makes the program relatively slow.

2. Java has high memory and performance requirements. This means that a lot of memory is needed.

3. It does not support low-level programming structures such as pointers.

4. There is no control over junk code in Java because Java does not include functions like delete(), free().

Disadvantages of C#

1. C# is an internal part of the .NET Framework, so the server running the application must be Windows-based.

2. C# is inflexible because it depends heavily on the .NET Framework.

History of C#

C#'s origins date back to the 2000s. In those years, Microsoft created this programming language for themselves. Originally, C# was a language developed in conjunction with Microsoft Visual Studio 2002 as a response to Java languages competing with JavaScript, that is, because Java could not meet Microsoft's demand. C# and Java have also been competing since the early days. Since then, C# has been approved as an international standard for computer programming and is used with a common language infrastructure.

There are many versions of C#, all of which have added more and more updates to the software.

Version 1 was designed as a simple, general-purpose programming language.

Version 2 was produced in 2005. It includes the ability to use iterators, which allow you to look at large chunks of data at once.

Version 3 was developed in 2007. New phrases (codes) were created; It is from this version that C# began to occupy higher positions in the trend than Java.

Version 4 was developed in 2010. Experts have created dynamic keywords and given it an elegance that other languages don't have.

Version 5 was developed in 2012. The possibility of asynchronization appeared.

Version 6 was released in 2013. Introduced new filters and initializer, making coding easier than before.

Version 7 was released in 2017. It has gained new capabilities, in particular .NET Core and the ability to use operating systems.

How to program in C#?

- ✓ Mobile programs
- ✓ Games (PC/Mobile)
- ✓ Desktop programs
- ✓ Programs for database
- ✓ Web applications
- ✓ Web services
- ✓ VR - Programs for Virtual Reality
- ✓ Websites

The first thing to do to start programming in C# is to download and install the coding environment. Because no program can be created without an environment. This environment is an editor called Visual Studio 2022.

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